

WHO Guidelines for malaria

Systematic reviews, background papers and other unpublished evidence considered in the development of recommendations

Prevention/Preventive chemotherapies

Section

4.2.2 Perennial malaria chemoprevention (PMC). In *WHO Guidelines for malaria*, 3 June 2022.

Title

Evaluation of Esu et al (2019) Cochrane review on intermittent preventive treatment of malaria in infants (IPTi)

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Note

Systematic review by Esu et al, entitled “Intermittent preventive treatment for malaria in infants” subsequently updated on 17 July 2021 to address feedback from Steinhardt and Carlson. The updated systematic review is available from:

<https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD011525.pub3>

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Evaluation of Esu *et al.* 2019 Cochrane Review on Intermittent Preventive Treatment of Malaria in Infants (IPTi)

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Version 1.3: 02 July 2021

Background

The WHO Global Malaria Program's Chemoprevention Guideline Development group, which was convened November 2020 to update the malaria chemoprevention guidelines, put forth a series of PICO (population, intervention, comparison, outcome) questions for systematic reviews, including question 3a on chemoprevention in infants. As a first step to respond to these questions, we have reviewed the 2019 Cochrane Review on intermittent preventive treatment of malaria in infants (IPTi)¹, given its suspected high quality, recency, and the low likelihood of additional studies of IPTi being published since the review publication. This document summarizes our evaluation of the 2019 Cochrane Review, and provides additional considerations for the GDG on this question.

Methodology

We used the published AMSTAR-2 Checklist², a critical appraisal tool for reviewing existing systematic reviews. Two independent researchers (LS and CC) read through the Cochrane Review and responded to the checklist questions. Here, we summarize the results of the AMSTAR checklist along with other relevant observations of the 2019 Cochrane Review. Where relevant, we point compare the 2019 Review to PICO question 3a: Should infants living in settings with perennial malaria transmission be given anti-malarial medicines as chemoprevention to reduce disease burden?

Findings

Methodological notes

- The review only includes randomized controlled trials (RCTs) but does not include other study designs (e.g., non-randomized quasi-experimental studies).

Outcome(s)

Primary outcomes:

- Clinical malaria (fever plus asexual parasitemia)

Other outcomes:

- Severe malaria
- Anemia
- Change in hemoglobin level
- Parasitemia

- Hospital admissions
- All-cause mortality
- Adverse events

Note that the additional PICO questions of drug/vaccine interactions and blood transfusions were not included as outcomes in Esu *et al.*

Evaluation against AMSTAR Checklist questions

1. Did the research questions and inclusion criteria for the review include the components of PICO?

Yes, it did for all components (PICO). An optional criterion (time frame for follow-up) was not explicitly specified (although the authors do note the follow-up times for the 12 included RCTs and presumably used these for outcome measurement). Timeframe for follow-up not specified (optional).

2. Did the report of the review contain an explicit statement that the review methods were established prior to the conduct of the review and did the report justify any significant deviations from the protocol?

Yes, there were clear methods outlined for the review. There did not appear to be any significant deviations from the protocol.

3. Did the review authors explain their selection of the study designs for inclusion in the review?

No, they did not. Only RCTs were included, but the rationale for doing this is not given in the review.

4. Did the review authors use a comprehensive literature search strategy?

Partial Yes (yes to searched at least 2 relevant databases; provided key word and/or search strategy; justified any restrictions; searched reference lists of included studies; searched trial/study registries; and conducted search within 24 months of the review completion. However, the authors did NOT mention consulting content experts in the field).

However, we noticed that although their search terms seem comprehensive (from the search strategy in Appendix 1), the CDC librarian retrieved nearly 3,000 records when she ran it, compared to the 153 records noted by the Cochrane Review authors. When she repeated it by limiting to RCTs in the search engines that allow this specification (even though the authors did not note this in their search strategy), she got 289 records.

5. Did the review authors perform study selection in duplicate?

Yes, as noted on page 11 of the Cochrane Review, both title and abstract screening as well as full-text screening were done by two independent reviewers.

6. Did the review authors perform data extraction in duplicate?

Yes, as noted on page 11 of the Cochrane Review, full text data abstraction performed by two independent researchers.

7. Did the review authors provide a list of excluded studies and justify the exclusions?

Yes. The list of excluded studies and reasons for exclusion is provided on page 42.

8. Did the review authors describe the included studies in adequate detail?

Yes (full); the included studies are detailed one-by-one on pages 26 – 41.

9. Did the review authors use a satisfactory technique for assessing the risk of bias (RoB) in individual studies that were included in the review?

Yes; the authors list 6 assessment criteria for RoB used, and an additional 5 criteria for cluster randomized trials. These cover all the risks listed in the AMSTAR checklist.

10. Did the review authors report on the sources of funding for the studies included in the review?

Yes; funding support is detailed on page 21.

11. If meta-analysis was performed, did the review authors use appropriate methods for statistical combination of results?

Yes, it appears the authors used appropriate methods for the meta-analyses conducted; the authors state on page 12 that they used a fixed-effect meta-analysis, but if moderate heterogeneity was detected and it was still appropriate to combine the trials, they used a random effects approach.

12. If meta-analysis was performed, did the review authors assess the potential impact of RoB in individual studies on the results of the meta-analysis or other evidence synthesis?

Yes; as stated on page 13, sensitivity analyses were done by including only trials that concealed the allocation adequately and had low incomplete outcome data (<10%) and by excluding cluster-randomized trials at high or unclear risk of bias for one of the additional cluster-specific risk of bias components.

13. Did the review authors account for RoB in individual studies when interpreting/discussing the results of the review?

Yes. Only one RCT included (Dicko et al) had high risk of bias. But the authors did a sensitivity analysis including and excluding this review.

14. Did the review authors provide a satisfactory explanation for, and discussion of, any heterogeneity observed in the results of the review?

Not fully. The authors did find moderate levels of heterogeneity (p. 18) for some of the outcomes, and in some cases downgraded the certainty of evidence because of this (p. 20). However, there does not appear to be a discussion of or explanation for these moderate levels of heterogeneity observed for selected outcomes.

15. If they performed quantitative synthesis, did the review authors carry out an adequate investigation of publication bias (small study bias) and discuss its likely impact on the results of the review?

The authors note on page 12 that they planned to construct funnel plots to look for evidence of publication bias, but that the number of trials in each meta-analysis were insufficient to make this informative. The authors note under ‘Certainty of the evidence’ (page 12) that publication bias was one of the five criteria used in the GRADE approach to assess the certainty of evidence. However, there is no additional mention of publication bias.

16. Did the review authors report any potential source of conflict of interest, including any funding they received for conducting the review?

No conflicts of interest were declared.

Other comments/notes

- The estimate for the main outcome of clinical malaria for IPTi with SP from the Schellenberg 2001 paper seems incorrect (Analysis 1.1). It is listed as having a rate ratio comparing IPTi versus placebo of 0.62 (95% CI: 0.42, 0.92) but in fact the protective efficacy, not the rate ratio, should be 62%, as listed in Table 2 of Schellenberg at all. Perhaps this data was mis-abstracted? In addition, it is unclear where the 95% CI comes from (it does not match the paper (not even the inverse). However, correcting this seeming mistake would likely have little if any difference on the point estimate for IPTi with SP (and for IPTi overall), given this trial’s weight of only 5.2% in the meta-analysis.
 - Using the original ReviewManager file from the Cochrane Review authors, we corrected the mis-abstracted efficacy estimate for Schellenberg 2001 trial and find the following:

	Original Esu review	With Schellenberg data corrected
IPTi with SP	0.79 (0.74, 0.85)	0.77 (0.66, 0.88)
IPTi overall (all drugs)	0.73 (0.65, 0.82)	0.69 (0.60, 0.80)

Thus updating the point estimate for Schellenberg 2001 makes little difference to the pooled efficacy estimate for IPTi-SP or IPTi overall.

- There are a few statements in the review that seem inconsistent. For example on page 18 in the results section, the authors state that, “IPTi with SP probably reduced the risk of asymptomatic parasitaemia among infants (rate ratio 0.66, 95% CI 0.56 to 0.79; 1 trial, 1200 participants; [Analysis 1.5](#)). Then on page 19 in the Discussion the authors state that, “IPTi with SP probably made little or no difference to the risk of asymptomatic parasitaemia and all-cause mortality (moderate certainty

evidence). Page 20 also notes when discussing IPTi with SP, “For the findings of no effect on parasitaemia and death from any cause...”

- It is unclear why certain results from studies with low risk of bias were not included in the main analyses but in additional tables starting on page 57.
 - For example, it is unclear why one study (Macete 2006), with a low risk of bias, had data on one outcome (severe malaria) but was not included in the meta-analysis, which included to other studies. The authors note on page 18 that “IPTi with SP may have made little or no difference on the risk of severe malaria (rate ratio 0.92, 95% CI 0.47 to 1.81; 2 trials, 1347 participants; [Analysis 1.2](#)). Another trial also found no difference in the risk of severe malaria ([Macete 2006 MOZ](#); see [Table 2](#)). However, the sample size was too small to detect or exclude clinically important differences”. Our understanding is that all relevant studies measuring the outcome of interest and with low risk of bias should be included, no matter how small the sample size. However, inclusion of Macete 2006 would make little difference to the point estimate or conclusions about IPTi and severe malaria.
 - This also pertains to why the Bigira 2014 study was not included in the main analyses on parasitemia after IPTi with DP or SP. The parasitemia with DP is included in the GRADE tables for IPTi with DP, but it’s unclear why these results are in an additional table but not the main analysis.

Summary table comparing PICO questions/considerations and Esu et al Review

The table below summarizes the Esu et al Cochrane Review characteristics for each of the PICO questions/factors proposed.

	PICO Questions	Esu et al review
Population	Children (up to 12 months of age) living in perennial malaria transmission settings	Children up to 12 months of age in settings with moderate-to- high malaria transmission
Background interventions	Standard of care in the place and at the time the study was conducted	Not specified
Intervention	Administration of full therapeutic courses of an antimalarial medicine at predetermined times	IPTi
Comparison	Either (i) no intervention, or (ii) alternative drug used for chemoprevention	Placebo or no treatment
Outcome	Confirmed clinical malaria* Severe malaria* Anaemia* Hospital admission (all-cause and malaria specific) Death (all cause) Safety (adverse events) Drug / vaccine interactions Parasite prevalence Blood transfusion	Confirmed clinical malaria Severe malaria Anaemia Hospital admission (all-cause) Death (all cause) Safety (serious adverse events and other adverse events) Parasite prevalence Change in hemoglobin
Timeframe	Reference periods are (i) the month after each dose, (ii) 12 months after dose 1, (iii)	Not explicitly specified (used the follow-up periods in the studies themselves (until 24 months of age in 8

	12 months after the last dose (for the assessment of the rebound phenomenon)	trials; a mix in the other 4 trials up to a maximum of 18 months of age)
Potential effect modifiers	Transmission intensity* Choice of drug Levels of existing drug resistance Timing of administration (in relation to peak transmission season) Age	Choice of drug (results are presented separately by type of drug used)
Additional considerations	Coverage of vector control Plasmodium species	

Summary

The Esu 2019 Cochrane Review appears to be a generally well conducted and thorough study that covers most of the PICO questions outlined by the GDG. There are a few quirks that we noted, but nothing that would appear to call into question the main results and conclusions of the review.

References

1. Esu, E.B., Oringanje, C. & Meremikwu, M.M. Intermittent preventive treatment for malaria in infants. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev* **12**, CD011525 (2019).
2. Shea, B.J., *et al.* AMSTAR 2: a critical appraisal tool for systematic reviews that include randomised or non-randomised studies of healthcare interventions, or both. *BMJ* **358**, j4008 (2017).

Update as of 25 February 2021

Abstraction and comparison of outcome effects data with that reported in Esu et al. Review

Given the error noticed in abstraction of data on protective efficacy against clinical malaria from the Schellenberg 2001 paper, all outcomes included in the Esu 2019 review were re-abstracted. Please see Appendix 1 (Excel sheet) for details. Red indicates a difference between the data we abstracted from the original article and that in Esu *et al.* A few notes on this are below.

- The only major difference appears to be the abstraction of data on protective efficacy against clinical malaria (outcome 1.1) from the Schellenberg 2001 paper, where Esu *et al.* appear to have abstracted protective efficacy as opposed to the rate ratio.
- For all other outcomes, including outcome numbers 1.2 (severe malaria), 1.3 (all-cause mortality), 1.4 (all-cause hospital admissions), 1.5 (parasitemia), 1.6 (anemia), and 1.7 (hematocrit), there were very minor differences in sample size, rate ratio and corresponding 95% confidence interval values were noted upon independent data abstraction and comparison back with values reported in Esu *et al.*, however none of these differences is of a magnitude that would be expected to alter the reported outcomes in Esu *et al.*
- Esu *et al.* did appear to calculate their rate ratios in some cases using the sample size of enrolled participants in the denominator, instead of person-time, but it is possible this was to standardize in cases where person-time was not available (e.g., for all-cause mortality outcomes for some papers that simply reported deaths in the study arms. In addition, we noted some inconsistencies where they split the placebo group for some three-arm studies for some outcomes but not for others.

Review of 12 included trials in Esu et al. Review for blood transfusions and vaccine-drug interactions

The following studies included in the Esu *et al.* systematic review examined or mentioned vaccine-drug interactions:

- **Chandramohan et al.** The immune response to EPI vaccines were taken when infants received IPT-1, IPT-3, and IPT-4; immune responses to EPI vaccines were being tested as part of a larger study commissioned by the IPTi consortium, and these results reported elsewhere.
- **Grobusch et al.** states at the end of the paper that the issue of vaccine drug interaction is being addressed in further studies by the IPTi Consortium underway across Africa.
- **Macete et al.** Serological responses to EPI vaccines were assessed in a subsample of study infants consecutively selected as they were coming to the clinic until the estimated sample size of 600 children was completed. No significant difference was found in GMTs, in the rates of serological responses to DTP/ OPV and hepatitis B, or in seroconversion rates to measles. Regarding the serological response to measles, the study had little statistical power to rule out noninferiority at the 5% level. However, further information is being gathered from other IPTi trials, and a pooled analysis of these trials is planned to confirm the safety of the intervention with regard to measles
- **Massaga et al.** We assessed infant antibody responses to vaccines given as part of the Expanded Programme on Immunisation. Secondary data analysis of adverse effects and effect of amodiaquine on diphtheria-pertussis and oral poliovirus vaccine responses were also done. The effect of treatment with amodiaquine on antibody responses to diphtheria-pertussis and oral poliovirus

vaccines was assessed by grouping infants receiving amodiaquine alone or amodiaquine plus iron and comparing them with infants who had received placebo or iron alone. Plasma antibody levels (IU/mL) were compared with the Mann-Whitney rank sum test.

- **Schellenberg et al.** Blood samples were collected to assess seroconversion to EPI vaccines (DTP/OPV at 9 months, measles at 12months). Serological responses to EPI vaccines were not affected by the intervention.

The following studies included in the Esu et al. systematic review examined or mentioned blood transfusions:

- The only mention of blood transfusions was in the following articles:
 - **Grobusch et al.** Two children in the SP group had severe anemia (hemoglobin <5 g/dL) requiring a blood transfusion.
 - **Gosling et al.** Participants with severe anemia (hemoglobin <5 g/dL) received a blood transfusion.

Review of CDC Library literature search

CDC Library replicated the literature search reported in Esu et al., which resulted 289 total records as compared with the 156 records resulted by Esu et al. Given the difference in records results, we reviewed all records identified by the CDC Library search and found the following:

- All 12 IPTi RCTs included in Esu et al were found by CDC Library search
- We did find one randomized controlled trial on IPTi outside of sub-Saharan Africa which was not included in the Esu et al. review, which was limited to sub-Saharan Africa. This study is: Senn et al. 2012. PLoS Medicine. Intermittent Preventive Treatment for Malaria in Papua New Guinean Infants Exposed to *Plasmodium falciparum* and *P. vivax*: Randomized Controlled Trial. The study includes protective efficacy (PE) against clinical malaria and concludes that IPTi had significant PE against *P. falciparum* infections but not against *P. vivax* infections.
- In addition, our search identified three randomized trials of IPT in children aged 2 – 36 months at enrolment, but that reported outcomes for all age groups combined and not separately for those <12 months old:
 - Verhof et al. 2002. The Lancet. Intermittent administration of iron and sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine to control anaemia in Kenyan children: a randomised controlled trial
 - Desai et al. 2003. Journal of Infectious Diseases. Randomized, controlled trial of daily iron supplementation and intermittent sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine for the treatment of mild childhood anemia in western Kenya
 - Terlouw et al. 2004. The American Journal of Clinical Nutrition. Relation between the response to iron supplementation and sickle cell hemoglobin phenotype in preschool children in western Kenya
- Additionally, CDC Library performed the same Esu et al literature search, except from Dec 2018 to present; no additional IPTi RCTs beyond those reported in Esu et al. and Senn et al. 2012 found in this search.

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